

Urban Road Network Resilience under Heavy Rainfall: Identifying Critical Links Using Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Networks

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Abstract

Urban road networks are increasingly exposed to climate-induced disruptions, particularly heavy rainfall events that reduce capacity, trigger rerouting, and amplify congestion. Identifying links whose disruption causes disproportionate network-wide impacts is essential for climate-resilient transport planning, yet conventional methods often overlook time-dependent cascading effects. This study develops a data-driven framework to identify critical road segments under heavy rainfall in Duisburg, Germany. Rainfall scenarios ranging from 40 to 90 mm/h were mapped onto the road network to adjust link-level speeds and identify road closures. Macroscopic dynamic traffic simulations generated baseline and disrupted traffic states, and were analyzed using a Spatio-Temporal Graph Attention Network with LSTM-based temporal modeling and multi-hop influence propagation. Results show that rainfall impacts extend beyond inundated links through rerouting and congestion propagation. Criticality concentrates in central corridors, especially urban collector and arterial roads, with evening peaks showing the strongest vulnerability. The framework provides a scalable GeoAI tool for climate-sensitive road criticality assessment.

Keywords: Road network resilience, flood disruption, critical link identification, graph neural networks, traffic simulation, climate-resilient transportation

1. Introduction

Climate change is associated with long-term shifts in the mean state and variability of the climate system over decades or longer (IPCC, 2023). One of its most consequential urban impacts is the increasing frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, including heavy rainfall. Such

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events can severely disrupt transportation systems by reducing road capacity, lowering vehicle speeds, causing localized closures, and triggering congestion that propagates across the wider network (Salvo et al., 2025; Sharif & Wittowsky, 2025a). Because urban road networks support commuting, logistics, emergency response, and access to essential services, their disruption can produce substantial social and economic consequences. Strengthening transportation resilience therefore requires identifying critical road links, defined here as links whose degradation or closure causes disproportionately large impacts on overall network performance, such as increased travel time, reduced accessibility, and lower network efficiency.

Identifying critical links under heavy rainfall is challenging because traffic responses are dynamic, spatially interdependent, and nonlinear. During rainfall or flooding, drivers may reroute away from affected links, while reduced visibility, lower pavement friction, and standing water can decrease effective speeds even on passable roads (Jafino et al., 2020; Sharif & Wittowsky, 2025b). These local disruptions can cascade through adjacent and functionally connected road segments, creating bottlenecks far from the original hazard location. As a result, link criticality under climate stress is not determined solely by whether a road is physically inundated, but also by how traffic redistribution interacts with network topology and time-varying demand.

Traditional approaches to road criticality assessment often rely on static graph-theoretic measures, such as betweenness, degree, or closeness centrality, or on static traffic assignment models (Ashja-Ardalan et al., 2025; Lu et al., 2024). While these methods provide useful insights into structural importance, they are limited in their ability to capture temporal traffic evolution, congestion propagation, and adaptive rerouting under weather-induced disruption. More recently, machine learning and deep learning approaches have been introduced to learn complex traffic patterns directly from data and to support scalable identification of vulnerable or influential links (Bachir et al., 2025; Jana et al., 2023). Among these methods, graph neural networks are particularly suitable for transportation applications because they explicitly represent the networked structure of road systems while learning spatial dependencies among links.

Spatio-temporal graph neural networks have shown strong potential for traffic flow prediction and network-state estimation because they combine spatial graph learning with temporal sequence modeling (Ta et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2026). Architectures that integrate Graph Attention Networks with recurrent models such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks can learn both local inter-link influence and temporal congestion dynamics (Huang et al., 2024). However, relatively few studies have explicitly combined spatio-temporal graph learning with climate-induced traffic stress, particularly under progressive heavy rainfall scenarios. This leaves an important methodological gap in understanding how localized hydrometeorological impacts translate into system-wide transport vulnerability.

To address this gap, this study develops a data-driven framework for identifying and ranking critical road segments under heavy rainfall. The framework integrates hydrodynamic flood simulations, macroscopic traffic assignment, a Spatio-Temporal Graph Attention Network, and a multi-hop influence propagation model. It is applied to the urban road network of Duisburg, Germany, using baseline traffic conditions and rainfall scenarios ranging from 40 to 90 mm/h. The study makes two main contributions. First, it incorporates multiple rainfall intensities into a graph-based road criticality framework, enabling climate-sensitive assessment of network

vulnerability. Second, it combines attention-based spatial learning, temporal traffic modeling, and influence propagation to estimate the systemic importance of road links under dynamic disruption conditions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area and Data

The empirical study focuses on Duisburg, Germany, a city covering approximately 232.8 km² and home to around half a million inhabitants (*Figure 1*) (Duisburg, 2026). Duisburg is located at the confluence of the Rhine and Ruhr rivers and hosts Europe’s largest inland port, Duisport, making it a major hub for freight transport, logistics, and regional mobility (Duisport, 2026). The city is also strongly connected to the regional and national motorway network. Given this geographic and infrastructural profile, Duisburg is particularly susceptible to the disruptive impacts of extreme weather events. Its estimated Climate Risk Index of 4.61 out of 10 for 2050 indicates a high level of climate-related vulnerability, primarily associated with storms, heavy rainfall, and heat stress. These characteristics make Duisburg a relevant and well-suited case study for analyzing urban transportation resilience under heavy rainfall conditions (iwkoeln, 2026; R2K-Klim+, 2026).

Heavy rainfall scenarios ranging from 40 to 90 mm/h were provided by Geomer GmbH and simulated using FloodAreaHPC, a raster-based hydrodynamic flood hazard model (FloodAreaHPC, 2026). Each scenario consisted of a one-hour precipitation phase followed by a two-hour recession phase. The model produced minute-resolution outputs of water depth, flow velocity, and flow direction at a spatial resolution of 1 m × 1 m (*Figure 1*). These outputs were used to estimate road-level exposure and to derive rainfall-induced traffic penalties.

Figure 1. Study area and simulated rainfall inundation of 90 mm/h in Duisburg (Source: <https://r2k.geomer-maps.de/>).

Traffic data were generated using macroscopic simulations in PTV VISUM (VISUM, 2025). The underlying traffic model was derived from the official municipal model developed in 2023. The model includes demand matrices and network assignments for motorized private transport, as well as public transport and bicycle components over a 24-hour period. It was calibrated to represent an average weekday condition for the reference year 2022, providing a consistent baseline for comparison with rainfall-induced disruption scenarios.

2.2. Methodological Workflow

The proposed framework consists of five main steps (*Figure 2*). First, flood depth was assigned to road links for each rainfall scenario, and link-level speed reductions or closures were derived. Second, dynamic traffic assignment was performed in PTV VISUM to estimate traffic states under baseline and rainfall conditions. Third, the road network was transformed into a spatio-temporal graph in which road links were represented as graph nodes and adjacency relations between road links were represented as graph edges. Fourth, a Spatio-Temporal Graph Attention Network was trained to learn dynamic dependencies between road links. Finally, learned attention weights were combined with a multi-hop influence propagation model to estimate and rank the systemic criticality of each road segment.

Figure 2. Integrated workflow for heavy-rainfall-based road link criticality assessment.

2.2.1. Identification of Flood-Affected Links

Flood exposure was estimated by spatially overlaying Duisburg’s road-link geometries with flood-depth outputs from the hydrodynamic model (40–90 mm/h). For each rainfall scenario, water depths were extracted for all road links intersecting the flood extent. A representative depth value was assigned to each link based on the maximum inundation depth observed along that link. This procedure was conducted separately for the rainfall phase and the subsequent recession periods to account for temporal changes in inundation.

Links were then classified according to their expected traffic functionality. Shallow inundation was treated as passable but associated with reduced speed, while links exceeding the safety threshold were considered impassable and closed in the traffic model. This classification follows established flood-disruption approaches that relate water depth to vehicle speed and road passability (Liu et al., 2026; Pregolato et al., 2017).

2.2.2. Traffic Simulation

To represent reduced drivability under inundated conditions, link water depth was converted into an allowable vehicle speed using the depth–disruption function proposed by Pregolato et al. (2017) (*Equation 1*).

$$v(w) = 0.0009w^2 - 0.5529w + 86.9448 \quad (1)$$

where w is the water depth in millimeters and $v(w)$ is the maximum permissible speed in km/h. Links with water depths of 300 mm or greater were treated as impassable and implemented as closed links in PTV VISUM. This threshold reflects the risk that deeper standing water can stall vehicles or create unsafe driving conditions.

Traffic assignment was performed for the baseline and for each rainfall scenario during the morning peak period, 06:00–09:00, and the evening peak period, 16:00–19:00. The resulting link-level outputs included traffic volume, speed, travel time, and volume-to-capacity ratio. These variables formed the basis for the subsequent spatio-temporal graph learning and criticality analysis.

2.2.3. Spatio-Temporal Graph Construction

The urban road network was represented using a link-as-node graph abstraction. In this representation, each road link becomes a graph node, and directed edges represent topological connectivity between adjacent road links. The resulting directed, weighted graph is defined as $G = (V, E, W)$; where V denotes the set of road-link nodes, E denotes the set of directed edges connecting adjacent links, and W represents edge weights, derived from physical road lengths.

To model temporal traffic evolution, a sliding-window of size $t = 3$ was applied. For each road-link node, the model used a sequence of historical traffic states of the past three hours to predict the subsequent traffic state. The input tensor included both dynamic and static link-level features (4D): speed, change in volume-to-capacity ratio, change in travel time, and normalized capacity. Speed, volume-to-capacity ratio, and travel time describe evolving congestion conditions, while normalized capacity provides information about the structural role and functional hierarchy of each link.

2.2.4. Spatio-Temporal Graph Attention Network

Spatio-Temporal Graph Attention Network was developed to learn dynamic dependencies among road links under baseline and rainfall conditions. While grounded in the T-GAT architecture proposed by Huang et al. (2024), our ST-GAT is specifically tailored to process climate-induced disruptions by integrating environmental shock features into the attention mechanism. The architecture combines a spatial attention module with a temporal sequence-learning module.

The spatial component uses a Graph Attention Network to estimate the relative importance of neighboring links at each time step. Each time step within the sliding window is processed independently to capture spatial dependencies. Unlike standard convolutions, the attention mechanism dynamically calculates spatial importance weights (α_{ij}) between a target node i and its neighboring nodes j . This allows the model to prioritize critical bottleneck connections based on real-time traffic interactions. The attention coefficient is computed using *Equation 2*.

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{\exp(\text{LeakyReLU}(a^T [Wh_i \parallel Wh_j]))}{\sum_{k \in N(i)} \exp(\text{LeakyReLU}(a^T [Wh_i \parallel Wh_k]))} \quad (2)$$

Where h_i and h_j represent the hidden state features of nodes i and j , W is a learnable linear transformation weight matrix, a is the attention mechanism parameter, $(\cdot \parallel \cdot)$ denotes the concatenation operation, and N_i denotes the set of first-order neighbors of node i .

The temporal component uses LSTM units to process the sequence of spatially enriched node embeddings. This allows the model to capture temporal dependence, including the persistence and accumulation of congestion following rainfall-induced capacity reductions.

To stabilize the subsequent influence propagation analysis, attention coefficients were averaged across the temporal window in the matrix α_{uv} (Equation 3).

$$\overline{\alpha}_{uv} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_{ij}^{(t)} \quad (3)$$

Where t represents the specific time step, and T is the total number of time steps within the historical observation window (in this study, $T = 3$).

During training, to address the extensive memory overhead of city-scale networks, a gradient accumulation strategy was employed to simulate full-batch training. Gradients are initialized to zero at the beginning of an epoch, and the computed loss for each sample is normalized by the total dataset size ($\frac{1}{N} \sum \text{loss}_i$). Furthermore, while optimization operates on a normalized scale, the model evaluates its performance using the Mean Squared Error. This metric calculates the unnormalized, physical error in actual speed units (km/h) against the free-flow speed, ensuring that the model remains transportationally accurate.

2.3. Influence Propagation and Criticality Ranking

The final step estimates each road link’s potential to propagate disruption through the network. The learned attention weights were combined with a distance-decay function to construct a sparse transition matrix (Huang et al., 2024). The transition matrix P is constructed by multiplying the consensus attention weights (α_{uv}) with a physical distance decay factor ($e^{-\beta \cdot d}$). Here, d represents the physical shortest-path distance between nodes, and β is a decay hyperparameter that controls how quickly a traffic shock dissipates over spatial distances. This formulation ensures that disruption propagation reflects both data-driven traffic interactions and spatial proximity.

The model simulates the multi-hop ripple effect of a traffic shock up to 3 spatial hops ($K = 3$) to quantify the network-wide influence. The actual shock was defined as the observed speed drop at the target time step. The cumulative influence score was calculated over three propagation hops using Equation 4.

$$\text{Influence} = \sum_{k=1}^3 (\text{Actual Shock} \times P^k \cdot 1) \quad (4)$$

Influence scores were averaged across overlapping temporal windows within each scenario and peak periods. The resulting mean influence score was used as the final criticality measure for ranking road links.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Spatio-Temporal Traffic Dynamics under Progressive Rainfall Stress

The analysis focuses on motorized private traffic, including passenger cars and freight vehicles, as represented in the PTV VISUM model. *Figure 3* compares traffic-volume differences between the baseline and two rainfall scenarios, 40 mm/h and 90 mm/h, during the morning peak hour from 06:00 to 07:00. The results show that rainfall-induced disruption is not confined to directly inundated links. Instead, affected links generate broader network responses as traffic is rerouted to alternative corridors, increasing pressure on roads that may not themselves be flooded.

Figure 3. Rainfall-induced changes in private motorized traffic volume during the morning peak (6:00 – 7:00): (a) 40 mm/h and (b) 90 mm/h.

Compared with baseline conditions, the average network speed decreases by 5.5% under the 40 mm/h scenario and by 8.7% under the 90 mm/h scenario. Total travel time increases more strongly, by 15.3% and 26.3%, respectively. This indicates that relatively moderate reductions in average speed can produce disproportionately large increases in travel time when congestion propagates through the network. Traffic volumes also decline by 13.0% and 21.5% under the 40 mm/h and 90 mm/h scenarios, respectively. This decline reflects the combined effects of link closures, capacity reductions, and redistribution of traffic flows across the network.

These findings demonstrate the nonlinear nature of rainfall impacts on urban mobility. The difference between the speed reduction and travel-time increase suggests that heavy rainfall affects not only individual link performance but also the efficiency of network-wide route choice and traffic distribution. In practical terms, this means that resilience planning should not focus exclusively on visibly flooded roads. Roads receiving diverted traffic may become equally important because they function as substitute routes during disruption.

3.2. Spatial Distribution of Critical Links

The proposed ST-GAT framework was first applied to baseline traffic conditions to identify the inherent structural criticality of the Duisburg road network. Under normal operating conditions, the model highlights major arterials, central corridors, and structurally important connecting links as the most influential components of the network. These links form the main conduits of inter-zonal movement and therefore have high systemic importance even in the absence of rainfall-induced stress.

Figure 4 shows the spatial distribution of critical links under baseline conditions and under 40 mm/h and 90 mm/h rainfall scenarios during morning and evening peak periods. Across scenarios, criticality is concentrated in the central urban area and along major access corridors. This pattern suggests that Duisburg's road-network vulnerability is shaped by both topological centrality and traffic demand concentration. Roads located in or near the urban core carry high levels of through traffic, local access traffic, and redistributed flows during disruption, making them particularly susceptible to cascading congestion.

The comparison between baseline and rainfall scenarios further indicates that heavy rainfall intensifies existing structural vulnerabilities rather than producing an entirely new pattern of criticality. In other words, many links that are important under normal conditions remain important under rainfall stress, but their influence becomes amplified when capacity is reduced or adjacent links are disrupted. This result is relevant for planning because it suggests that resilience investments targeted at structurally central corridors may provide benefits across both everyday congestion management and extreme-weather preparedness.

3.3. Road-Class-Specific Criticality

To evaluate how criticality is distributed across the road hierarchy, critical links were categorized according to German Guidelines for integrated network design (*Richtlinien für integrierte Netzgestaltung*, 2008). *Table 1* shows that urban-oriented road classes dominate the critical-link set across all rainfall intensities.

The category “DV Sammelstraße/Zufahrt”, representing urban local collector and access roads, has the highest share of critical roads in all scenarios, ranging from 18.54% under 40 mm/h rainfall to 22.08% under 90 mm/h rainfall. This result is particularly important because collector and access roads often function as connectors between local streets and higher-capacity arterials. During rainfall-induced disruption, these links can become essential for maintaining local accessibility and enabling rerouting. Their high criticality therefore reflects their role as both access infrastructure and redistribution channels.

The category “CIII 1FS 50”, representing urban municipal arterial roads with a single carriageway and a 50 km/h speed limit, also contributes strongly to the critical-link set, with values between 17.32% and 18.83%. Its high and stable representation indicates that these roads maintain systemic importance across all rainfall intensities. Urban district distributor roads, especially “CIV 1FS 45”, form the third major group, with shares of approximately 14–15%.

Figure 4. Spatial patterns of road-link criticality under baseline and heavy-rainfall scenarios.

Table 1. Distribution of critical road links by functional road class under heavy rainfall scenarios.

Road Classification Notation	Road Description	40 mm/h	50 mm/h	60 mm/h	70 mm/h	80 mm/h	90 mm/h	Intersection
DV Sammelstraße/Zufahrt	Urban local collector/access road	18.54%	19.73%	19.68%	22.29%	21.77%	22.08%	18.76%
CIII 1FS 50	Urban municipal arterial, single carriageway, 50 km/h	18.15%	17.32%	18.83%	18.13%	17.93%	17.82%	17.57%
CIV 1FS 45	Urban district distributor road, single carriageway, 45 km/h	14.33%	15.23%	14.24%	14.65%	14.47%	14.4%	15.19%
CII 1FS 50	Urban regional arterial road, single carriageway, 50 km/h	5.53%	5.21%	5.84%	4.9%	5.23%	5.48%	5.03%
CIV 1FS 35	Urban district distributor road, single carriageway, 35 km/h	4.52%	4.13%	4.4%	4.04%	3.84%	3.62%	4.2%
CIII 1FS 60	Urban municipal arterial road, single carriageway, 60 km/h	4.47%	4.79%	4.97%	4.56%	4.65%	4.7%	4.45%
CIII 2FS 50	Urban municipal arterial road, dual carriageway, 50 km/h	4.04%	4.18%	3.91%	3.82%	4.04%	4.27%	4.13%
BII 2FS 50	Rural regional access/distributor road, dual carriageway, 50 km/h	2.74%	2.7%	2.7%	2.45%	2.38%	2.43%	2.52%
BIII 1FS 60	Rural access/distributor road, single carriageway, 60 km/h	2.22%	2.2%	2.2%	2.11%	2.2%	1.77%	2.34%
CIII 1FS 30	Urban municipal arterial road, single carriageway, 30 km/h	2.07%	2.13%	1.84%	1.91%	2.07%	1.98%	2.11%

A notable finding is the relative stability of the criticality distribution across rainfall intensities. Most road classes show only minor fluctuations between 40 and 90 mm/h scenarios. This suggests that increasing rainfall severity amplifies the intensity of disruption but does not fundamentally reorganize the functional hierarchy of critical links. The “intersection” column further supports this interpretation, showing that many links are repeatedly identified as critical across scenarios. This persistence is valuable for infrastructure planning because it helps distinguish consistently critical links from scenario-specific hotspots.

In contrast, rural road categories such as “BII 2FS 50” and “BIII 1FS 60” show comparatively low shares of critical links, mostly below 3%. This does not imply that these roads are unimportant locally, but rather that their disruption has a smaller modeled impact on city-wide traffic performance. Overall, the results highlight the dominant role of urban collector, distributor, and arterial roads in maintaining network resilience during heavy rainfall.

3.4. Temporal Variation in Network Vulnerability

The temporal analysis reveals substantial differences between morning and evening peak vulnerability. *Figure 5* shows that evening peak conditions consistently produce a broader and more severe distribution of critical links than morning peak conditions. Under the 90 mm/h scenario, 343 links reach moderate to high influence scores between 2 and 3 during the evening

peak, compared with 123 links during the morning peak. In addition, links with influence scores between 1 and 2 expand to 2,908 during the evening peak.

This difference suggests that the evening network state is more vulnerable to cascading disruption. Several mechanisms may explain this pattern. Evening peak travel demand is often more spatially dispersed than morning commuting demand, involving not only work-to-home trips but also shopping, leisure, logistics, and local service trips. This can create more complex route-choice patterns and increase dependence on collector and distributor roads. Moreover, if rainfall disruption occurs after several hours of daily network loading, congestion may accumulate and reduce the ability of the network to absorb additional capacity losses.

The results therefore indicate that link criticality is not fixed but depends on the interaction between network structure, rainfall intensity, and time-of-day traffic conditions. From a resilience-planning perspective, this finding is important because emergency traffic management strategies should be temporally differentiated. Links that appear manageable during the morning period may become highly critical during the evening peak under the same rainfall intensity.

Figure 5. Distribution of network influence scores across peak periods and rainfall scenarios.

3.5. Limitations

Although the proposed framework effectively captures spatio-temporal traffic dependencies and rainfall-induced disruption propagation, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, training spatio-temporal graph neural networks on city-scale transport networks is computationally demanding. The construction of high-dimensional tensors across nodes, features, time steps, and scenarios requires substantial memory and processing capacity. Techniques such as gradient accumulation mitigate this issue but do not eliminate the computational burden. Second, validating macroscopic criticality rankings remains challenging. Empirical observations of full network-wide failures are rare, and ground-truth data on cascading

urban traffic disruptions during extreme rainfall are often unavailable. As a result, the model evaluation relies primarily on simulated traffic states rather than observed disruption events. Third, the study depends on macroscopic traffic simulations. Although these simulations are calibrated and physically grounded, they cannot fully reproduce all behavioral responses during real extreme-weather events, such as risk perception, spontaneous route switching, or non-compliance with closures.

4. Conclusion

This study developed a GeoAI-based framework for identifying critical urban road links under heavy rainfall conditions. The central research problem was to determine how rainfall-induced capacity reductions and link closures propagate through an urban road network and which road segments contribute most strongly to systemic disruption. To address this problem, hydrodynamic flood simulations, macroscopic traffic assignment, a Spatio-Temporal Graph Attention Network, and a multi-hop influence propagation model were integrated and applied to the road network of Duisburg, Germany.

The results show that heavy rainfall affects urban mobility not only through direct inundation but also through cascading congestion and rerouting effects. Even when speed reductions appear moderate at the network level, total travel times increase substantially, indicating nonlinear disruption propagation. Criticality is spatially concentrated in central urban corridors and major access routes, while urban collector, distributor, and arterial roads consistently dominate the set of critical links across rainfall intensities. The analysis also reveals strong temporal variation: evening peak conditions produce broader and more severe criticality patterns than morning peak conditions, especially under the 90 mm/h rainfall scenario.

These findings demonstrate that road criticality under climate stress is dynamic, context-dependent, and shaped by the interaction between network topology, traffic demand, and environmental exposure. The proposed framework contributes to transportation resilience research by combining spatio-temporal graph learning with rainfall-specific disruption modeling and influence-based criticality ranking. For planners and decision-makers, the approach provides a scalable screening tool to identify priority corridors for targeted adaptation measures, traffic management, and emergency planning. More broadly, the study illustrates how GeoAI methods can support climate-resilient urban infrastructure planning in increasingly hazard-prone cities.

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